

Immunological Detection Methods, Cytokines Test and C-Reactive Protein Test In Women Infected With *Trichomonas Vaginalis*

Muslim Abbas Allu^{1*}

¹Nursing Department, Technical Institute of Zakho/ Duhok, University of Duhok polytechnic
 * Corresponding Author: Muslim Abbas Allu, Email: muslim.allu@dpu.edu.krd

APA citation: Allu, M.A. (2025). Immunological Detection Methods, Cytokines Test and C-Reactive Protein Test In Women Infected With *Trichomonas Vaginalis*. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 5(3), 173-176

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 17 Oct 2025</p> <p>Keywords: <i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> Cytokines and CRP Immunofluorescence ELISA</p>	<p><i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> is the most prevalent non-viral sexually transmitted infection, Nucleic acid amplification tests and point-of-care tests are newly available diagnostic methods that can be conducted on a variety of specimens, potentially allowing highly sensitive testing and screening of both women and men at risk for infection, The most commonly used method of diagnosis is a direct microscopic We developed an indirect enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for the detection of <i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i> which is both rapid and sensitive (detection limit of approximately 100 trichomonads per ml). that the ELISA is a significant improvement over the wet mount method for the diagnosis of trichomoniasis. as well as immunological staining of fixed specimens, Is a technique that permits visualization of virtually many components in any given tissue or cell type. This broad capability is achieved through combinations of specific antibodies tagged with fluorophores. Assays for anti trichomonad antibodies in either serum or vaginal secretions, and indirect immunofluorescence also was important as well as the cytokines test they allow your immune system to mount a defense if germs or other substances that can make you sick enter your body. And CRP test measures the level of C-reactive protein in a sample of your blood.</p>

1. Introduction

Trichomonas vaginalis is a highly prevalent parasitic infection that causes the sexually transmitted disease (STD) trichomoniasis. *Trichomonas vaginalis* parasites preferentially infect the urethra in men and women, and vaginal and vulvar sites in women. Pharyngeal and respiratory infections in newborns born to mothers with vaginitis caused by *T. vaginalis* may represent yet another important manifestation of trichomoniasis (1). In addition, an increased incidence of endometritis during pregnancy has been implicated with this infection (2).

2. Morphology

Studied parasite of all the trichomonas. This urogenital pathogen varies in size and shape, with the average length and width being 10 and 7 µm, respectively (2). Physicochemical conditions do alter the appearance of the parasite. In axenic culture, the shape of the protozoan tends to be more uniform, i.e., pear shaped or oval (3), but the parasite takes on more amoeboid appearance when attached to vaginal epithelial cells (3,4). *T. vaginalis* has only trophozoite stage with a size of (7-32 µm) and is pear shaped. It possesses 5 flagellates, 4 of which are forward with a fifth flagella that bends back along the undulating membrane and lacks the cyst stage and possesses a central nucleus and axostyle, Trophozoites divided by binary fission. The parasite is an aerotolerant anaerobe that dissolves whole carbohydrates into short chains of organic acids Especially (acetate and lactate) Regardless of the presence of oxygen. The parasite produces hydrogen molecules in the absence of oxygen, and this reaction occurs in hydrogenases that like mitochondria (which are not present) in *T. vaginalis*, which are energy producing organelles surrounded by two membranes (5).

3. Pathogenesis

Trichomoniasis accounts to almost half of curable sexually transmitted infections according to the world health organization (6,7) Women with trichomoniasis may be asymptomatic or may experience various symptoms, including vaginal discharge and vulvar irritation. Men with trichomoniasis may experience no gonococcal urethritis but are frequently asymptomatic. (8). The general infection areas include urethra, external

genitalia, prostate, and epididymis. (9) It is also a known leading cause of prostatitis and urethritis. (10) Furthermore, serious complications may be associated with trichomoniasis such as premature rupture of the placental membranes, premature labor, and low birth weight in pregnant women infection, infertility, cervical cancer, pelvic inflammatory disease, birth outcomes, and increase in human predisposition to immunodeficiency virus (HIV), its transmission, and acquisition. (11,12) Infection with *T. vaginalis* is associated with higher genital HIV-1 levels. The treatment of women infected with *T. vaginalis* results in a 4.2-fold reduction in the quantity of HIV-1 in vaginal secretions. (11) Some recent studies have shown that trichomoniasis may be considered as one of the predisposing factors for some human disease such as prostate and cervical cancer. (13) The outcome of infection with *Trichomonas* may be due to genetic variability of the isolates and the host immune response. (14) *T. vaginalis* infection is based on their covey of the motile organism in the vaginal discharge or mucosal scraping of the vagina in female and urethral discharge in male, and it is able to detect the protozoa at a concentration as low as three organisms (15). The traditional clinical diagnosis of vaginal infection is based on a history of patient, clinical finding observed during the vaginal specimen. This last one provides the most objective information. A microscope wet amount examination of the specimen permits, detection of the motile protozoa *T. vaginalis* (16). Although *T. vaginalis* is the most common cause of non-viral STD (17).

4. Immunology and Serology Tests (ELISA)

Several methods have been developed for the detection of the protozoan. These include in vitro culture of the organism, direct microscopic examination of smears both with and without the aid of vital stains (21, 22, 25, 32), immunological staining of fixed specimens (22, 24). Is a technique that permits visualization of virtually many components in any given tissue or cell type. This broad capability is achieved through combinations of specific antibodies tagged with fluorophores. Consequently, the possible applications in research and patient care are numerous, assays for anti-trichomonas antibodies in either serum or vaginal secretions (18, 22, 23, 26, 27), and indirect immunofluorescence (19). and serological methods suffer from the poor correlation between antibody titers and active infection (22,

23, 27). Thus, it appears likely that immunological detection of trichomonas antigens will prove to be the most sensitive approach to the diagnosis of trichomonas's Examination of sera or vaginal secretions for antibodies to the parasite offers little promise of being of diagnostic utility (18, 22, 23, 25, 27), primarily because of the lack of correlation between the presence of antibodies and an active infection. Using indirect immunofluorescence microscopy, several investigators (22, 25) reported that while 80 to 90% of patients with trichomonas's had circulating antibodies to the protozoan, 13 to 17% of a control population of patients did also. Their results in testing vaginal secretions for IgG or IgA antibodies to *T. vaginalis* were even less encouraging. Currently, there are no reports in the literature in which an ELISA is used for the detection of *T. vaginalis* antigens in clinical specimens. Here we have reported the development of a rapid, sensitive ELISA for the detection of *T. vaginalis* antigens in vaginal secretions. organisms have been observed by several serologic-based techniques including ELISA (18, 19), indirect immunofluorescence (22, 28, 29), and radio immunoprecipitation (19). Although investigators are currently studying the antigenic composition of the organism with monoclonal antibodies (20,22), data from these reports indicate that obtaining a single monoclonal antibody which recognizes all isolates of the organism could prove to be problematic. In addition, the two-site design of our assay requires antibodies with good affinity both bound to the solid phase and as detectors in solution in contrast to one-site assays developed for detecting the protozoan (e.g., immunofluorescence) (22). The ELISA used for antigen detection is rapid, easy to perform, and provides superior sensitivity over the wet mount method. The utility of such a format would be a major step in diagnosing it may be that there is systemic inflammation in the pathway leading to birth both at term and preterm (30)

5. CRP, Cytokines and CBC Test

Cytokines are signaling proteins that help control inflammation in your body. They allow your immune system to mount a defense if germs or other substances that can make you sick enter your body. Too many cytokines can lead to excess inflammation and conditions like autoimmune diseases. A c-reactive protein test measures the level of c-reactive protein (CRP) in a sample of your blood. CRP is a protein that your liver makes. Normally, you have low levels of c-reactive protein in your blood. Your liver releases more CRP into your bloodstream if you have inflammation in your body. High levels of CRP may mean you have a serious health condition that causes inflammation.

The increased C-reactive protein and cytokines in the sera of *T. vaginalis* infected women suggests that the impact of the immunoinflammatory reaction to the parasite exceeds the boundaries of the reproductive tract mucosa (31). a significant decrease in concentration of Hb, PCV in infected women with *T. vaginalis* infection, may be due to hemolysis of RBCs and phagocytosis by *T. vaginalis* parasite and the increased bleeding through menstrual cycle and this leads to decrease in the number of RBCs and the hemolysis of RBCs may lead to decrease in the Hb concentration (10;11). One of the most frequent causes of anemia in *T. vaginalis* infection, a decrease in MCV, MCH and MCHC in women infection with *T. vaginalis* parasite, a decrease in MCV may be due to a decrease in Hb and decrease INCH is caused by iron deficiency anemia that lead to decrease in formation of Hb in RBCs The results also provided decrease in level of PCV in patient women may be due to a decrease in RBCs counts or due to decrease in MCV caused by decreased level of Hb in RBCs. About 50% of infected women with *T. vaginalis* punctuate hemorrhages can be observed (2). a significant increase in WBCs; these due to an increase in the number of monocyte, lymphocyte, neutrophils, and Basophils because the infection with this parasite causes stimulation immune system of host humeral and cellular. The results also revealed Basophilia associated with patients who suffering from *T. vaginalis* infection; these phenomena are not fully understood. The reason for this observation may be attributed to allergy disorder which is one of symptoms of *T. vaginalis* infection these allergies.

6. HIV and Trichomoniasis

The incidence of *T. vaginalis* infection is higher among HIV-infected individuals compared with those who are not HIV-infected (32). Up to 52.6% of HIV-infected women have been found to be connected with *T. vaginalis* (33,34). Among HIV-infected women, *T. vaginalis* infection is significantly associated with pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) (35), and treatment of *T. vaginalis* infection is associated with significant decreases in genital tract viral load and vaginal HIV viral shedding (36, 37). Among HIV-infected men,

data are scant. Both HIV acquisition and transmission have been studied in relationship to *T. vaginalis* infection. *Trichomonas vaginalis* infection is epidemiologically associated with HIV acquisition. A prospective study of 3297 African HIV-serodiscordant couples found that *T. vaginalis* infection is an independent risk factor for HIV acquisition; *T. vaginalis* infection of the female partner was associated with an increased per-act probability of her acquiring HIV during sex (OR, 2.57 [95% CI, 1.42–4.65]) (38). *Trichomonas vaginalis* infection also has been associated with a potential for increased transmission of HIV. *T. vaginalis*–uninfected controls showed that *T. vaginalis*–infected women who were effectively treated for *T. vaginalis* infection were less likely to shed HIV vaginally at 3 months' post treatment compared with baseline (RR, 0.34 [95% CI, 0.12–0.92]), while there was no change for *T. vaginalis*–uninfected women (37). Several studies have investigated the implications of maternal *T. vaginalis* infection during pregnancy; the most established association is with preterm delivery. A prospective cohort study of 13 816 pregnant women in 5 US cities found that *T. vaginalis* infection at midgestation was significantly associated with low birth weight (aOR, 1.3 [95% CI, 1.1–1.5]), preterm delivery (aOR, 1.3 [95% CI, 1.1–1.4]), and preterm delivery of a low birth-weight infant (aOR, 1.4 [95% CI, 1.1–1.6]) (39). Further study is urgently needed to determine whether treatment of trichomoniasis during pregnancy can reduce such complications.

7. Infertility

Trichomoniasis could plausibly interfere with male and female fertility, although few studies have been conducted to investigate this potential connection. Among men, an in vitro study showed that *T. vaginalis* parasites can adhere to, immobilize, and phagocytose sperm cells (40). A Turkish study found that among 80 infertile men, 2.5% had a positive *T. vaginalis* test by PCR, but serology was not available (41). Among women, a study of 321 women with tubal infertility in Seattle found that the RR of tubal infertility was significantly higher among women who self-reported a history of trichomonas's (adjusted RR, 1.7 [95% CI, 1.1–2.6]) (42).

8. Treatment

Medications approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for treatment of trichomonas's include metronidazole (since 1963) and tinidazole (since 2004). Standard therapy consists of either metronidazole or tinidazole in a single 2-g dose taken orally, or, if necessary, intravenously. The CDC also recommends an alternative regimen of metronidazole 500 mg orally twice a day for 7 days. Tinidazole has a half-life of approximately 12.5 hours, compared with a half-life of 7.3 hours for metronidazole (43).

9. Prevention

Trichomoniasis is an STD that can be avoided by abstaining from sex. Among sexually active individuals, the most effective way to prevent trichomoniasis is by using condoms consistently and correctly during vaginal-penile sexual encounters (44,45). Periodic presumptive treatment for high-risk individuals such as sex workers can effectively reduce trichomoniasis (44,45). sex workers can effectively reduce trichomoniasis (47-49). sex workers can effectively reduce trichomoniasis (45,46). and *T. vaginalis* infections can also prevent associated conditions such as HIV infections and complications of pregnancy.

10. Conclusion

Trichomonas vaginalis infection is highly prevalent, often asymptomatic, and easily communicable between sex partners. Infection is associated with significantly increased risks of HIV acquisition and transmission, pregnancy complications including preterm delivery, PID among HIV-infected women, and other conditions. Usually, trichomoniasis can be cured with single-dose therapy of an appropriate nitroimidazole antibiotic (eg, metronidazole or tinidazole), but women who are also infected with HIV should receive therapy for 7 days. Antimicrobial resistance is an emerging concern. Screening should be provided at least annually to all HIV-infected women. Increase in cytokines and CRP concentrations in the serum of women infected with *T. vaginalis*, indicates a stimulation of the humoral immune response during the infection with *T. vaginalis*. and decrease of HB, PCV, MCV, MCH and MCHC due to a decrease in Hb and decrease in MCHC is caused by iron deficiency anemia that lead to decrease in formation of Hb in RBCs decrease in level of PCV and the hemolysis of RBCs may lead to decrease in the Hb concentration and increase of level lymphocyte, monocyte, neutrophil and basophil in infected woman's

RESEARCH ARTICLE

because the infection with this parasite causes stimulation immune system of host humeral and cellular, as well as allergy disorder is one of symptoms of T. vaginalis infection.

Funding sources:

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies.

Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- McClelland RS. Trichomonas vaginalis infection: can we afford to do nothing? *The University of Chicago Press*; 2008.
- Arroyo R, Gonzalez-Robles A, Martinez-Palomo A, Alderete JF. Signalling of Trichomonas vaginalis for amoeboid transformation and adhesion synthesis follows cytoadherence. *Mol Microbiol.* 1993; 7:299–309.
- Heath J P. Behaviour and pathogenicity of Trichomonas vaginalis in epithelial cell cultures: a study by light and scanning electron microscopy. *Br J Vener Dis.* 1981; 57:106–117.
- Honigberg B M, King V M. Structure of Trichomonas vaginalis Donne. *J Parasitol.* 1964; 50:345–364.
- Schwebke JR, Burgess D. Trichomoniasis. *Clinical microbiology reviews.* 2004;17(4):794–803
- WHO, Global Incidence and Prevalence of Selected Curable Sexually Transmitted Infections 2008, *World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland*, 2012.
- D. F. Harp and I. Chowdhury, “Trichomoniasis: evaluation to execution,” *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, vol. 157, no. 1, pp. 3–9, 2011.
- Warner L, Klausner JD, Rietmeijer CA, et al. Effect of a brief video intervention on incident infection among patients attending sexually transmitted disease clinics. *PLoS Med.* 2008; 5:919–27.
- K. Bouchemal, C. Bories and P. M. Loiseau. “Strategies for prevention and treatment of Trichomonas vaginalis infections”. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 811–825, 2017.
- J. J. Lee, H. S. Moon, T. Y. Lee, H. S. Hwang, M. Ahn and J. Ryu. “PCR for diagnosis of male Trichomonas vaginalis infection with chronic prostatitis and urethritis”. *The Korean Journal of Parasitology*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 157–159, 2012.
- R. S. McClelland, L. Sangare, W. M. Hassan, L. Lavreys, K. Mandaliya, J. Kiarie, J. Ndinya-achola, W. Jaoko and J. M. Baeten. “Infection with Trichomonas vaginalis increases the risk of HIV-1 acquisition”. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*, vol. 195, no.5, pp. 2-6, 2007.
- O. E. Chinyere, I. I. Romanus, O. N. Collins, N. Okoro and O. E. Anthonia. “Trichomonas vaginalis associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes: Implications for maternal health care delivery system in South Eastern Nigeria”. *Biomedical Research*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 568–574, 2012.
- J. H. Fowke, X. Han, J. F. Alderete, K. A. Moses, L. B. Signorello and W. J. Blot. “A prospective study of Trichomonas vaginalis and prostate cancer risk among African American men.” *BMC Research Notes*, vol. 9, p. 224, 2016.
- F. Mercer, F. G. I. Diala, Y. Chen, B. M. Molgora, H. Ng and P. J. Johnson. “Leukocyte lysis and cytokine induction by the human sexually transmitted parasite Trichomonas vaginalis”. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, vol. 10, pp. 1-19, 2016
- Dard C, Marty P, Brenier-Pinchart M-P, et al. Management of toxoplasmosis in transplant recipients: an update. *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther* 2018; 16:447–60. 10.1080/14787210.2018.
- Seema, S. and Artikapil, G. (2008). An update on Trichomonas vaginalis, *Indian J. Sex Transm Dis*, 29 (1): 7-14.
- Daron, C. E. (2009). Office laboratory diagnosis of vaginitis: clinician-performed tests compared with a rapid nucleic acid hybridization test available on line at (<http://nd.articles.com/articles/mi-m-m-0689is-n6-v4lai-179136341>), 02. 05.
- Alderete, J. F. 1984. Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay for detecting antibody to Trichomonas vaginalis: use of whole cells and aqueous extract as antigen. *Br. J. Vener. Dis.* 60:164-170.
- Alderete, J. F., L. Suprun-Brown, L. Kasmala, J. Smith, and M. Spence. 1985. Heterogeneity of Trichomonas vaginalis and discrimination among trichomonal isolates and subpopulations with sera of patients and experimentally infected mice. *Infect. Immun.* 49:463-468.
- Bennett, B. D., J. Bailey, and W. A. Gardner. 1980. Immunocytochemical identification of trichomoniasis. *Arch. Pathol. Lab. Med.* 104:247-249
- Greenwood, J. R., and K. Kirk-Hillaire. 1981. Evaluation of acridine orange stain for detection of Trichomonas vaginalis in vaginal specimens. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 14:699.
- Hipp, S. S., M. W. Kirkwood, and H. A. Gaafar. 1980. Screening for Trichomonas vaginalis infection by use of acridine orange fluorescent microscopy. *Sex. Transm. Dis.* 6:235-238.
- Krieger, J. N., K. K. Holmes, M. R. Spence, M. F. Rein, W. M. McCormack, and M. R. Tam. 1985. Geographic variation among isolates of Trichomonas vaginalis: demonstration of antigenic heterogeneity by using monoclonal antibodies and the indirect immunofluorescence technique. *J. Infect. Dis.* 152: 979-984.
- Mason, P. R. 1979. Serodiagnosis of Trichomonas vaginalis infection by the indirect fluorescent antibody method. *J. Clin. Pathol.* 32:1211-1215.
- Mathews, H. M., and G. R. Healy. 1983. Evaluation of twoserological tests for Trichomonas vaginalis infection. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 17:840-843.
- Spence, M. R., D. H. Hollander, J. Smith, L. McCaig, D. Sewell, and M. Brockman. 1980. The clinical and laboratory diagnosis of Trichomonas vaginalis infection. *Sex. Transm. Dis.* 7:168-171.
- Street, D. A., D. Taylor-Robinson, J. P. Ackers, N. F. Hanna, and A. McMillan. 1982. Evaluation of an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for the detection of antibody to Trichomonas vaginalis in sera and vaginal secretions. *Br. J. Vener. Dis.* 58:330-333.
- Su, K. E. 1982. Antibody to Trichomonas vaginalis in human cervicovaginal secretions. *Infect. Immun.* 37:852-857.
- Su-Lin, K. E., and B. M. Honigberg. 1983. Antigenic analysis of Trichomonas vaginalis strains by quantitative fluorescent antibody methods. *Zentralbl. Bakteriol. Parasitenkd. Infektionskr. Hyg. Abt. 1 Orig. Reihe A* 69:161-181.
- Szmarch, H., E. MaLyszko, A. Wronski, and E. Niczyporuk. 1983. Diagnostic and epidemiologic significance of multinuclear and round forms of Trichomonas vaginalis. *Z. Hautkr.* 58: 1179-1182.
- Torian, B. E., R. J. Connelly, R. S. Stephens, and H. H. Stibbs. 1984. Specific and common antigens of Trichomonas vaginalis detected by monoclonal antibodies. *Infect. Immun.* 43:270-275.
- Connelly, R. B., B. E. Torian, and H. H. Stibbs. 1985. Identification of a surface antigen of Trichomonas vaginalis. *Infect. Immun.* 49:270-274.
- Rein, M. F., and T. A. Chapel. 1975. Trichomoniasis, candidiasis, and the minor venereal diseases. *Clin. Obstet. Gynecol.* 18:73-88.
34. Anderson, Brenna LMD, Cosentino, Lisa A BS, Simhan, Hyagriv NMDMS, and Hillier, Sharon L. PhD Systemic immune response to Trichomonas vaginalis infection during pregnancy. *Sex Transm Dis.* 2007;34(6):392-6.
- Crosby RA, Charnigo RA, Weathers C, Caliendo AM, Shrier LA. Condom effectiveness against non-viral sexually transmitted infections: a prospective study using electronic daily diaries. *Sex Transm Infect* 2012; 88:484–9.
- Garcia PJ, Holmes KK, Carcamo CP, et al. Prevention of sexually transmitted infections in urban communities (Peru PREVEN): a multicomponent community-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet* 2012; 379:1120–8.
- Balkus JE, Richardson BA, Mandaliya K, et al. Establishing and sustaining a healthy vaginal environment: analysis of data from a randomized trial of periodic presumptive treatment for vaginal infections. *J Infect Dis* 2011; 204:323–6.
- Benchimol M, de Andrade Rosa I, da Silva Fontes R, Burla Dias AJ. Trichomonas adhere and phagocytose sperm cells: adhesion seems to be a prominent stage during interaction. *Parasitol Res* 2008; 102:597–604.
- Ozdemir E, Kelestemur N, Kaplan M. Trichomonas vaginalis as a rare cause of male factor infertility at a hospital in East Anatolia. *Andrologia* 2011; 43:283–5.
- Sherman KJ, Daling JR, Weiss NS. Sexually transmitted diseases and tubal infertility. *Sex Transm Dis* 1987; 14:12–6.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

- Wood BA, Monro AM. Pharmacokinetics of tinidazole and metronidazole in women after single large oral doses. *Br J Vener Dis* 1975; 51:51–3.
- Mullins TL, Rudy BJ, Wilson CM, Sucharew H, Kahn JA. Incidence of sexually transmitted infections in HIV-infected and HIV-uninfected adolescents in the USA. *Int J STD AIDS* 2013; 24:123–7.
- Miller M, Liao Y, Wagner M, Korves C. HIV, the clustering of infections, sexually transmitted and sex risk among African American women who use drugs. *Sex Transm Dis* 2008; 35:696–702.
- Cu-Uvin S, Ko H, Jamieson DJ, et al. Prevalence, incidence, and persistence or recurrence of trichomoniasis among human immunodeficiency virus (HIV)-positive women and among HIV-negative women at high risk for HIV infection. *Clin Infect Dis* 2002; 34:1406–11.
- Moodley P, Wilkinson D, Connolly C, Moodley J, Sturm AW. *Trichomonas vaginalis* is associated with pelvic inflammatory disease in women infected with human immunodeficiency virus. *Clin Infect Dis* 2002; 34:519–22.
- Anderson BL, Firnhaber C, Liu T, et al. Effect of trichomoniasis therapy on genital HIV viral burden among African women. *Sex Transm Dis* 2012; 39:638–42.
- Kissinger P, Amedee A, Clark RA, et al. *Trichomonas vaginalis* treatment reduces vaginal HIV-1 shedding. *Sex Transm Dis* 2009; 36:11–6.
- Hughes JP, Baeten JM, Lingappa JR, et al. Determinants of per-coitalact HIV-1 infectivity among African HIV-1-serodiscordant couples. *J Infect Dis* 2012; 205:358–65.
- Cotch MF, Pastorek JG II, Nugent RP, et al. *Trichomonas vaginalis* associated with low birth weight and preterm delivery. The Vaginal Infections and Prematurity Study Group. *Sex Transm Dis* 1997; 24:353–60.